

THE ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL TRUST AND JOB SATISFACTION IN MEDIATING THE INFLUENCE OF ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE ON ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AND WORK ENGAGEMENT OF POLICE MEMBERS IN THE SOUTHEAST SULAWESI REGIONAL POLICE

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze and evaluate the influence of: organizational justice on organizational trust, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work engagement, as well as analyzing the mediating role of organizational trust and job satisfaction to see the impact of organizational justice on organizational commitment and work engagement. The object of this research is the Regional Police of Southeast Sulawesi Province. The respondents used are police officers in each existing unit with the rank of non-commissioned officer and officer with a total of 350 people. The research model uses a structural model so that the research data collected is analyzed using PLS. The results of this research reveal that organizational justice has a positive and significant influence on organizational trust, job satisfaction and organizational commitment, respectively. Justice was found to have no effect on work engagement. Organizational trust was found to have an influence on job satisfaction, organizational commitment and work engagement. Job satisfaction was influence on organizational commitment and work engagement. Organizational commitment has a significant influence on work engagement.

Keywords: Organizational Justice, Organizational Trust, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Work Engagement.

INTRODUCTION

The Indonesian police are one of the government bodies which has the task of maintaining security and public order as stated in Article 30 paragraph 4 of the 1945 Constitution that the National Police as an instrument of the state to maintain security and public order is tasked with protecting, protecting, serving and enforcing the law. To carry out their duties, the Police need human resources who are competent and have a spirit of loyalty to their agency and country. Human resources in an organization are always the main key. Lack of commitment and engagement from human resources will have a negative impact on organizational implementation. Studying the behavior of organizational members is important because cultivating and retaining potential organizational members is not easy. One way that organizations can retain their members is to continue to increase their commitment and attachment to the organization and their work (Sun et al, 2022; Ha and Lee, 2022).

Organizational commitment is a form of loyalty and involvement of organizational members which is reflected in their loyalty and awareness of working for the success of organizational goals. Commitment is defined as an individual's level of loyalty, values, attitudes, practices and feelings, level of attachment and dedication to the organization (Meyer and Herscovich, 2001:300). Apart from organizational commitment, in relation to increasing organizational members' loyalty to their

organization, it is necessary to look at the aspect of commitment to work which is known as work engagement. Work engagement is a general cognitive state of a person who identifies himself with his work to determine self-image and achieve self-esteem. Bakker and Leiter (2010) state that work engagement refers to the cognitive condition of organizational members characterized by high motivation and how active, integrated and efficient the organization is. Every member of an organization who has work engagement is more open to their environment, has enthusiasm and is more productive so they can change their work environment to be more enjoyable. (Rich, Lepine and Crawford, 2010)

The good organizational commitment and work engagement of organizational members cannot be separated from the causal factors that can influence the level of these two aspects. In various literature studies also referring to organizational behavior theory, it can be seen that one of the aspects that influences the commitment and work engagement of organizational members is organizational justice felt by its members (Sun et al, 2022; Ha and Lee, 2022; Lambert et al, 2020). Organizational justice is a concept of balance in treating members, which is expected to be implemented by organizations to trigger the growth of a sense of commitment and engagement in work.

Organizational justice generally has a good influence on the formation of organizational commitment. In previous studies, it has been revealed that the perception of justice felt by members will encourage trust in their organization, as well as encourage them to work better and produce high commitment to the organization. Furthermore, Unaam et al (2021) also concluded that organizational justice plays an important role in creating member commitment to their organization (Ha & Lee, 2022; Jang et al, 2019). Furthermore, focusing on social exchange theory reveals that members who feel strong organizational justice tend to feel obliged to work at a higher level and give all their energy to maximize the work they do (McFarlin and Sweeney, 1992; Sun et al, 2022).

Furthermore, organizational commitment and work engagement are also influenced by organizational trust factors. Dirks and Ferrin (2002) revealed that an important factor in building organizational commitment is the existence of a relationship of trust that is built in the organization, both a relationship of trust in the organization itself, trust in superiors and trust in colleagues (Bahremand and Parkouh, 2020; Loes and Tobin, 2020). Apart from that, trust was also found to have an important role in increasing members' work engagement. Members' trust in their superiors and co-workers can encourage them to work with deep involvement (Mubashar et al (2022). Someone who has a high level of trust in their organization will provide high dedication to their contribution to achieving goals (Martiman et al, 2020; Klasson and Rehman, 2021).

Furthermore, aspects of job satisfaction in the literature review were found to have an influence on organizational commitment (Sun et al 2022; Ha & Lee, 2022). Emotional attachment develops through positive effects resulting from supportive work experiences with the work environment, including the organization. Experiences according to organizational members that are very satisfying tend to increase affective commitment to the organization, experiences that are dissatisfying can reduce feelings of attachment (Rivai, 2005: 138).

Looking at existing literature concepts, trust and job satisfaction have an important contribution to increasing organizational commitment held by members. Trust and satisfaction are closely related to the sense of justice perceived by members. Sun et al (2022) reveal that organizational justice can create trust, when an organization always behaves fairly towards its members, trust will arise automatically where organizational members assume that the organization will not cause them significant losses. Ha & Lee (2022) also revealed the same thing that organizational justice has a good impact on the perceived trust of organizational members. However, from the research findings of Sun et al (2022), organizational trust cannot increase the role of organizational justice in creating organizational commitment.

This research is a development of previous research (Sun et al, 2022) which examined organizational justice, organizational trust, job satisfaction and commitment, as well as developing it by including aspects of work engagement (Ha and Lee, 2022) as one aspect of commitment to work. This research is interesting for several reasons. First, this research discusses two aspects of member engagement, namely the aspect of attachment to the organization, in this case organizational commitment, and the aspect of attachment to work, in this case work engagement. The relationship between these two aspects is an interesting topic to research, because research usually only covers one aspect. Next, research by Sun et al (2022) provides direction on the use of co-worker trust as an indicator that can complement aspects of measuring organizational trust, where this research can further refine previous research.

The Regional Police is a level of the Indonesian National Police which is tasked in provincial areas based on Article 13 of Law no. 2 of 2002 states that the main task of the Regional Police is to maintain security and public order, enforce the law and provide protection, protection and service to the community. Police officers are required to have a strong commitment to their organization because they are one of the main gates providing a sense of security and order in society. Police officers who do not have work commitment and engagement will have a bad impact, not only on their work, but also on the image of their organization in society. For this reason, it is necessary to strengthen the commitment of police officers so that they carry out their duties and responsibilities as well as possible. In an effort to optimize the effectiveness of achieving organizational goals, it is hoped that members will have commitment to the organization and engagement with their work.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Justice

Justice is a complex phenomenon that may have different meanings for different people and different interpretations in cultures, religions and civilizations. In a literature review, Rawis (1971) in Kercher (2004) states that justice refers to an individual's subjective evaluation of the correctness of the treatment they receive, meaning that what is considered fair is based on a person's perception of justice and not on objective reality (Bazerman, 1993). This implies that judgments of fairness are relative and not absolute for different people. Organizational justice originates from Equity Theory which suggests individuals make judgments about fairness based on the quantity they provide (input) compared to the quantity they receive (output). Ensuring organizational fairness should be a priority for organizations, it can reduce workplace deviance, absenteeism, and encourage positive attributes such as trust and progressive

communication. Organizational justice refers to the extent to which organizational members perceive workplace procedures, interactions and outcomes to be fair.

Justice is a balance between the input an individual brings to a job and the results they obtain from that job (Simamora, 2009:451). According to Greenberg (1993) organizational justice is the perceived fairness of procedures in the organization. According to Bies and Trip (1996) organizational justice is related to the rules and social norms that regulate, must be distributed, the procedures used to make decisions and how organizational members are treated interpersonally. Furthermore, Colquitt et al (2001) revealed that organizational justice is an individual's perception regarding the objectivity of decisions, the decision-making process in the organization and the influence of perceptions on behavior. Furthermore, Koopman (2003) explains that organizational justice is the result of perceptions given by individuals subjectively regarding the treatment they receive from other people around them.

Organizational Trust

Organizational trust is a development of previous trust theories. Organizational trust is related to dependence on someone and is directed towards cooperation in the most efficient use of resources. Shockley, et al. (2000), organizational trust is the willingness of an organization, based on its culture and communication behavior in relationships and transactions, to be vulnerable to other individuals, groups, or organizations on the basis of the belief that they are competent, honest, open, caring, reliable, and identified with goals. Norms and values. Furthermore, Rousseau, et al (1998) define organizational trust as a psychological state consisting of the intention to receive rewards based on positive expectations of other intentions or behavior. In the organizational scope, organizational trust is a general description shown by members of the organization (Steers, 1977). Organizational trust shows that organizational members feel confident in the organization or company and its management, so that organizational members feel that their commitment has been fulfilled. If this is not achieved then members of the organization will feel like they have failed and are neglected regarding the roles and results that have been achieved by members of the organization.

Theory and empirical research have confirmed that trust plays a role in responding to crises in organizations. According to DeJanasz et al, (2012) organizational trust is an important foundation in a healthy work environment. Without organizational trust, organizational members will focus on self-protection which will weaken the desire to be cooperative and collaborative, damage motivation, and thwart productivity and innovation at work. Organizational trust includes the level of sensitivity of organizational members to every aspect within the organization that they will carry out all activities based on its scope. There are three main forms of organizational trust consisting of management trust, supervisor trust, and coworker trust. These three forms of trust differ depending on the target of what is believed (Robertson, et al, 2012; Tan & Tan, 2000).

Job Satisfaction

In the public sector, job satisfaction is the most important element where the greater the level of satisfaction felt by organizational members, the greater the drive they have to work better (Dhurup, et al 2016). Spector (1997) explains that job satisfaction refers to how a person feels about his job and the different aspects of his job. In other words, job satisfaction is a development of just feelings of liking (satisfaction) or disliking

(dissatisfaction) with his job. Job satisfaction is related to effectiveness or emotional response to various aspects of work (Kreitner and Kinicki, 2003). Mathis and Jackson (2001) stated that job satisfaction is a positive emotional state from evaluating one's work experience. Job satisfaction has many aspects in general, the stages observed are satisfaction with the job itself, salary, recognition, the relationship between supervisors and workers, and opportunities for advancement.

Job satisfaction is the emotion of organizational members within the scope of their work, where simply job satisfaction is related to the extent to which employees like their work (Oshagbemi 2003). It represents an individual's evaluation of their own work. This includes a general evaluation regarding whether individuals have positive feelings towards job factors or characteristics and the work environment (Ahmadi et al. 2012). Job satisfaction can explain whether an employee is satisfied and happy with his job. Job satisfaction is a function of rewards and values related to work (Divkan et al. 2013).

Organizational Commitment

Meyer and Allen (1997) state that organizational commitment is a belief that binds employees to the organization where they work, which is demonstrated by loyalty, involvement in work, and identification with the organization's values and goals. According to Colquitt, et al. (2009) stated that organizational commitment influences whether employees will remain members or leave the organization to pursue other work. Meanwhile, according to Gibson, et al (2010) stated that organizational commitment involves three attitudes, namely: identification with organizational goals, feelings of involvement in organizational tasks, and loyalty to the organization.

Commitment is also related to the state of a person's alignment with their organization, as expressed by Robbins (2008) in his statement that organizational commitment is a situation where an employee supports a particular organization and its goals and desire to maintain membership in that organization. Research conducted by Baron and Greenberg (1990) also states that commitment means an individual's strong acceptance of the goals and values of the organization, where the individual will try and work and have a strong desire to remain in the company.

Organizational commitment has an impact on members and the organization where they work. According to Sopiah (2008) the impact of organizational commitment can be seen on two sides, namely from the perspective of the organization and members of the organization. Viewed from an organizational perspective, employees who have low commitment will have an impact on turnover behavior, high absenteeism, increased work inertia and less intensity to remain as employees in the organization, lower quality and lack of loyalty to the organization. Viewed from an employee's point of view, employees who have high commitment will have an impact on improving the employee's career. An employee who has a good organizational commitment attitude will increase his performance. This is based on an attitude of involvement in the organization and a desire to survive and understand the goals of the organization.

Work Engagement

Work engagement can be defined as a positive, satisfying and work-related state of mind which characteristically has three components, namely vigor, dedication and absorption (Schaufeli et al, 2002). Coetzee and Roythorne-Jacobs (2007) define work engagement as a positive, satisfying, work-related state of mind characterized by high

levels of energy and mental resilience while working, a willingness to invest effort in one's work, perseverance in the face of difficulties, having enthusiastic and proud of their work, feel inspired and challenged by their work, and feel happy immersed in their work. Work engagement is also viewed as a persistent and pervasive cognitive-affective state that is not focused on specific objects, events, individuals or behaviors and an energetic state in which organizational members are dedicated to excellent performance at work and are confident in its effectiveness (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004; Schutte, et al, 2000). Engaged employees have an energetic and affective relationship with their work activities and see themselves as able to face the demands of their work fully (Schaufeli, et al, 2002).

Bakker, et al (2008) call work engagement a state of positive motivational-affective fulfillment, which is characterized by the dimensions of vigor, dedication and absorption, where most studies on work engagement show the same perception by measuring vigor, dedication and absorption. Acts as a key indicator for measuring work engagement (Schaufeli et al., 2002). Schaufeli and Bakker, (2004) stated that Vigor is a high level of energy and mental resilience when working. Bakker and Demerouti (2008) state that people who have dedication have a high intensity of involvement in every task given to them, especially they have a sense of pride in their work that can inspire other people to be like them. Apart from that, absorption is a deep concentration at work. Individuals with these characteristics always enjoy their work to the point of being carried away by their work. In addition, Schaufeli et al., (2002) believe that engaged employees find it difficult to disengage from work.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework Model

Hypothesis

Organizational justice that is positively perceived by organizational members will influence their trust in the scope of work and the organization. Sun et al (2022) explained in their research that organizational justice which includes distributive and procedural justice positively influences organizational trust. Ha & Lee (2022) also revealed that organizational justice has a significant impact on the trust that organizational members have in their organization. Research conducted by Ngeleshi and Dominic (2020) also revealed that employees' organizational trust can be

influenced by the fair attitude shown by the organization and the tools within it. Another finding that also supports this influence is from Pathardikar et al (2022) who explain that justice is able to have a significant impact on the trust that employees have. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 1: Organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on organizational trust

In line with social-exchange theory, an organization that is fair to its employees will create job satisfaction because what they give to the organization is reciprocated according to what they expect. Research from Sembiring et al (2019) reveals that satisfaction can be created from a sense of fairness felt by employees in the workplace. Ngeleshi and Dominic (2020) concluded in their research that organizational justice, especially distributive justice, makes a major contribution to achieving job satisfaction for organizational members. Pathardikar et al (2022) also revealed that overall organizational justice influences the level of perceived job satisfaction. Novitasari et al (2020), and Silitonga et al (2020) also concluded that there is a positive and significant influence between organizational justice and job satisfaction. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 2: Organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

There is a lot of research which reveals that organizational justice is related to perceived organizational commitment, that employees' perceptions where they feel that their organization is treating them fairly will increase the commitment they have to the organization. Ha & Lee (2022) in their research revealed that organizational justice has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment. Other findings from Unaam et al (2021) also reveal the same thing that organizational justice, especially good procedural justice, will increase the loyalty of organizational members because they feel involved in the organization and this influences the commitment they feel. Lambert et al (2020) revealed that to increase organizational commitment, it is necessary to implement optimal organizational justice towards its members. Findings from Apriono et al (2021) reveal that organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. This is in line with Hamzah's (2020) findings that organizational justice has a significant effect on organizational commitment. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 3: Organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment

Research conducted by Ha & Lee (2022) revealed that organizational justice can create deep involvement from organizational members in their work, this is related to the good distributive and procedural and interactional aspects that are created. Apriono et al (2021) also revealed that the implementation of organizational justice is able to form positive perceptions of organizational members and ultimately form commitment. Findings from Rahman and Karim (2022) also reveal that organizational justice can form strong work engagement in employees to produce the performance expected by the organization. Furthermore, findings from Hermanto and Srimulyani (2022) provide an illustration that organizational justice has a positive and significant influence on work engagement. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 4: Organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on work engagement

Sun et al (2022) in their research explained that police officers' trust in their organization will give them peace of mind at work and guarantee that they will get their rights at work, and this causes the level of job satisfaction for police officers to be high. Findings from Ngeleshi and Dominic (2020) also reveal that organizational trust can provide job satisfaction, where when this trust is related to management or supervisors, when this trust matches their perceptions, the satisfaction they feel will be higher. Pathardikar et al (2022) in their research concluded that organizational trust can influence job satisfaction. This is the same as the findings from Bahremand and Parkouh (2020) who also concluded that employees' organizational trust will lead them to satisfaction at work. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 5: Organizational trust has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

Trust is an important factor that can convince someone to commit further to the organization where they work. Commitment that is not based on trust will make employees quickly bored and have the desire to leave. Findings from Ha & Lee (2022) explain that high trust in the organization can form positive organizational commitment in employees. Research results from Bahremand and Parkouh (2020) also explain that organizational members' trust in co-workers and supervisors can give them positive signals about attitudes and behavior that will not harm them, and ultimately this will strengthen the commitment they have to the organization. Loes and Tobin (2020) and Vito and Mekuri-Ndimele (2020) each found that organizational trust can significantly influence employees' organizational commitment. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 6: Organizational trust has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment

Work engagement is an important factor in achieving organizational goals. Trust can increase the work engagement of organizational members (Mubashar et al, 2022). The findings of Martiman et al (2020) explain that deep work involvement can be formed in employees when they have high trust in their organization that the effort they put in will not be in vain. Klasson and Rehman (2021) in their research revealed that organizational trust has a positive impact on work engagement. Khawaja and Soomro (2021) also stated in their research that trust can form strong work engagement. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 7: Organizational trust has a positive and significant effect on work engagement

The concept of job satisfaction has long been discussed which needs to be improved by organizations to create employee commitment to their organization. Sun et al (2022) explain that job satisfaction can encourage the creation of strong organizational commitment in employees. Vickovic and Morrow (2020) also revealed that job satisfaction has a positive and significant impact on organizational commitment. Other findings reveal that perceived job satisfaction can encourage employees to work better and maintain their organization to achieve its expected goals (Pathardikar et al, 2022). Novitasari et al (2020) explained that affective, normative and continuity commitment

can be created well when employees in the organization have a level of satisfaction at work. Bahremand and Parkouh (2020) also found that job satisfaction has a significant impact on organizational commitment. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 8: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment

Someone who feels job satisfaction will have a strong motivation to be involved in their work and dedicate themselves to the work they do. Novianti et al (2023) through their research revealed that job satisfaction has an important role in increasing employee work engagement. Lan et al (2020) also revealed that someone who feels satisfaction can influence their engagement behavior at work. Hossen et al (2020) in their research concluded that job satisfaction has a significant influence on work engagement. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 9: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on work engagement

Organizational Commitment to Work Engagement

Organizational commitment and work engagement in general are interconnected aspects where commitment includes a person's view of the organization, while work engagement is more about the work carried out. Through their research, Ha & Lee (2022) revealed that the organizational commitment possessed by employees will encourage them to have deep involvement in work, in this case related to work engagement. Hamzah (2020) also revealed that organizational commitment has a significant influence on work engagement.

Meanwhile, Cao et al (2019) also tested the engagement aspect, where their research revealed that organizational commitment has an important role in encouraging employees to continue to work better. Finally, Gomes and Marques (2022) also concluded that organizational commitment has an influence on work engagement. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 10: Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on work engagement

Based on social-exchange theory, it is explained that there are elements that provide mutual benefits. Organizational justice is one of the triggers for the emergence of organizational trust. Organizational justice on the other hand can also shape organizational commitment. Organizational commitment which is formed from a sense of justice felt towards the organization will be able to strengthen organizational members' sense of trust in their organization.

Ha and Lee (2022) explain that organizational justice can create organizational commitment where organizational justice also has a significant impact on organizational trust. Furthermore, findings from Pathardikar et al (2022), and Lambert et al (2020) also concluded that organizational justice is able to influence organizational commitment and organizational trust in employees.

However, other findings from Sun et al (2022) suggest a different thing, namely that organizational commitment cannot mediate the influence of organizational justice on organizational trust. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 11: Organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment through organizational trust

Job satisfaction can be created from a sense of fairness which is perceived positively by employees and this can encourage the formation of organizational commitment. Research from Pathardikar et al (2022) concluded that job satisfaction is a good mediator in supporting organizational justice to increase employees' organizational commitment. Novitasari et al (2020) also revealed in their findings that there is a significant influence between organizational justice and organizational commitment which is mediated by job satisfaction.

Furthermore, findings from Silitonga et al (2020) also reveal the same thing that job satisfaction can be a good mediator in supporting increased organizational commitment through organizational justice. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 12: Organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment through job satisfaction

Members' trust in the organization can arise from the sense of fairness given by the organization to its members, through this sense of fairness it can influence the work engagement they have. A fair organization can create employee trust in the organization which ultimately increases work engagement.

Research from Ha & Lee (2022) reveals that organizational trust has a strong mediating influence in supporting the influence of organizational justice on work engagement. Mubashar et al (2022) also revealed that someone who has high trust in the organization due to organizational justice will have a higher level of work engagement. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 13: Organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on work engagement through organizational trust

An organization that is perceived as fair by its members can encourage a higher level of satisfaction with their work, and ultimately influence the engagement they have with the organization. Pathardikar et al (2022) and Hossen et al (2020) revealed that organizational justice can influence the work engagement of organizational members, and will be stronger when they feel job satisfaction.

Novitasari et al (2020) also revealed that organizational justice can shape job satisfaction which ultimately influences behavior at work. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated: Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 14: Organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on work engagement through job satisfaction

Organizational commitment can be a good link to combine the organizational perspective and the perspective of the work being carried out. The findings from Ha and Lee (2022) show that organizational commitment is able to mediate the influence of organizational justice felt by employees in increasing their work engagement.

Apart from that, findings from Hamzah (2020) also support this relationship, that justice can increase employees' desire to be deeply involved in work when this is accompanied by strong organizational commitment. Based on these findings, in this research a hypothesis can be formulated:

Hypothesis 15: *Organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on work engagement through organizational commitment*

RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a quantitative approach with a positivist paradigm with an explanatory research type where data collection is carried out using cross-sections. Based on the data collection method, this study is a survey using a cross section, through a questionnaire in the form of a questionnaire where data is only collected once. The survey method is a research activity carried out at a certain time to explain the condition of the respondent.

This research takes as its object the scope of the Regional Police of Southeast Sulawesi Province. The population in this study was all police personnel in the Southeast Sulawesi Provincial Police, totaling 2.800 personel consisting of non-commissioned officers and officers. Of this number, 350 police personnel were used as research respondents based on the formulation results and research limitations.

This research data was then collected using a survey method using a questionnaire where the data that had been collected was analyzed using Partial Least Square analysis (PLS).

Measurements

In collecting data for this research, each variable was assessed based on the indicators of each variable which had been determined based on concepts and analysis from experts. In organizational justice, it is measured by distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice (Robbins and Judge, 2015; Sun et al, 2022; Ha & Lee, 2022).

Organizational trust uses measurements from Haynes et al (2020) and Sun et al (2022) which consist of co-worker trust, supervisor trust and management trust. Furthermore, job satisfaction adopts two indicators, namely intrinsic satisfaction and extrinsic satisfaction (Stride et al, 2007).

Organizational commitment uses indicators from Mayer and Allen (1990) which consist of affective commitment, continuous commitment and normative commitment. Finally, work engagement uses Schaufeli et al., (2002) which consists of vigor, dedication, and absorption.

RESULT

In this research, the characteristics of the National Police personnel who are the respondents in this research will be explained, consisting of each work unit within the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police. The characteristics of respondents in this study are intended to reveal the identity of respondents obtained through distributing questionnaires divided into 350 questionnaires. These characteristics are presented in table 1 below.

Table 1: Characteristics of Research Respondents

Characteristics	Category	Frequency (Person)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Man	294	84
	Woman	56	16
	Amount	350	100
Last education	Senior High School	148	42.3
	Diploma (D3)	15	4.3
	Strata 1 (S1)	124	35.4
	Strata 2 (S2)	60	17.1
	Strata 3 (S3)	3	0.9
	Amount	350	100
Age (Years)	20 – 29	104	29.7
	30 – 39	99	28.3
	40 – 49	128	36.6
	> 50	19	5.4
	Amount	350	100
Work Period (Years)	2 – 10	136	38.9
	11 – 19	74	21.1
	20 – 28	122	34.9
	> 29	18	5.1
	Amount	350	100
Rank	Non-commissioned officer	283	80.9
	Commissioned Officer	67	19.1
	Amount	350	100
Marital status	Not married yet	75	21.4
	Marry	270	77.1
	Widow widower	5	1.4
	Amount	350	100

Based on the presentation in table 1, it shows that the majority of police personnel at the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police are men, namely 294 people or 84%, while there are 56 female personnel or 16%. Where the highest level of education among police personnel is a high school education level, namely 148 people or 42.3%, and a strata 1 (S1) education level with a total of 124 people or 35.4%, which shows that the majority of police personnel have this level of education. to face and carry out every task and responsibility given to them.

Regarding the characteristics of age and length of service, it was found that the majority age range was 40 years - 49 years with a total of 128 people or 36.6%, with the majority having a working period of 2 - 10 years with 136 people or 38.9%. %, and range 20 – 28 years with a total of 128 people or 34.9%. Through this data, it can be concluded that police personnel serving in the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police are generally of a mature age and have extensive experience in carrying out law enforcement duties and have a good view of the organization and its work. Apart from that, in general, police officers in the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police have high experience in carrying out their duties to protect, protect and serve the community. Regarding marital status, the majority of police personnel are married with a total of 270 people or 77.1%, where marital status can influence police officers in their work and in viewing their organization, someone who is married and has greater responsibilities will view organizational justice to the extent that their job satisfaction is different from unmarried personnel.

Structural Model Testing

Structural model testing is evaluated by looking at the R2 value of the latent variable using the Geisser Q Square test. Inner model testing can be seen from the R-Square on the similarities between latent variables. The results of the R-Square calculation can be seen in Table 2 below.

Table 2: R-Square Test Results

	R Square
Organizational Trust	0.806
Job satisfaction	0.866
Organizational Commitment	0.854
Work Engagement	0.866

Based on the calculation results in Table 2, to test the feasibility of the model, the total coefficient of determination is used. A Q-square value greater than zero (0) indicates that the model has predictive relevance, while a Q-square value of less than zero (0) indicates that the model lacks predictive relevance. To determine the Q-square value, the following formula is used:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1-R12) * (1-R22)$$

Q-square calculations using R-square data in the three models above can be done as follows:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1-0.806) * (1-0.866) * (1-0.854) * (1-0.866)$$

$$Q^2 = 0.99$$

Based on the Q-square (Q2) calculation, a Q-square value of 0.99 is obtained. This figure can be interpreted to mean that the research model can explain the contribution of the influence of the organizational justice variable on organizational trust, job satisfaction, organizational commitment and work engagement of 99%, so the model is has been built to have a very good predictive relevance value or prediction level.

Research Hypothesis Testing

Direct effect

Direct effect testing was carried out on 10 (ten) hypotheses used in this research. This hypothesis was tested using the structural equation method with the SEM-PLS Ver. 3, by testing the significance of the path coefficients in the model. A summary of the results of the path analysis calculations in this research can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3: Recapitulation of Research Results

Research Hypothesis				Path Coefficient	t-statistics	p-values	Results
H1	Organizational Justice	→	Organizational Trust	0.898	46,934	0,000	Accepted
H2	Organizational Justice	→	Job satisfaction	0.471	5,817	0,000	Accepted
H3	Organizational Justice	→	Organizational Commitment	0.278	2,927	0.004	Accepted
H4	Organizational Justice	→	Work Engagement	0.031	0.433	0.665	Rejected
H5	Organizational Trust	→	Job satisfaction	0.485	6,220	0,000	Accepted

H6	Organizational Trust	→	Organizational Commitment	0.215	2,767	0.006	Accepted
H7	Organizational Trust	→	Work Engagement	0.159	2,144	0.033	Accepted
H8	Job satisfaction	→	Organizational Commitment	0.460	4,016	0,000	Accepted
H9	Job satisfaction	→	Work Engagement	0.410	4,160	0,000	Accepted
H10	Organizational Commitment	→	Work Engagement	0.362	3,012	0.003	Accepted

Based on the results of hypothesis testing in table 3, it can be seen that in hypotheses 1,2, and 3 it was found that organizational justice on organizational trust has a path coefficient value of 0.898, and has a t-statistic value of 46.934 (>1.96) with a P-value of 0.000 (< 0.05) which means there is a significant influence between organizational justice and organizational trust. Meanwhile, the influence on job satisfaction has a path coefficient value of 0.471, t-statistic of 5.817 (>1.96) with a P-value of 0.000 (<0.05) which also means that there is a significant influence between organizational justice and job satisfaction. As well as its influence on organizational commitment, it was found to have a path coefficient of 0.278 with a significance of 0.004 (< 0.05), which means there is a significant influence between organizational justice and organizational commitment. Based on these results, it can be concluded that organizational justice can significantly and positively influence organizational trust, job satisfaction and perceived organizational commitment. On this basis, hypotheses 1, 2 and 3 proposed in this study are declared accepted. Meanwhile, in testing the influence of organizational justice on work engagement through Hypothesis 4, it was found to have a path coefficient value of 0.031, as well as a t-statistic of 0.433 (<1.96) with a P-value of 0.665 (> 0.05) which means that there is an influence which is not significant between organizational justice and work engagement. On this basis, hypothesis 4 proposed in this study is declared rejected.

Next, looking at the role of organizational trust in influencing job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work engagement as seen in hypotheses 5, 6, and 7, it can be seen that all of them are significant and positive where their influence on job satisfaction has a path coefficient of 0.485 with a t-statistic of 6.220 (> 1.96) and a P-value of 0.000 (< 0.05), while its influence on organizational commitment has a path coefficient of 0.215, and a t-statistic of 2.767 (> 1.96) with a P-value of 0.006 (< 0.05), and is also related to work engagement where the path coefficient value is 0.159, t-statistic is 2.144 (>1.96) with a P-value of 0.033 (<0.05). Based on these results, it can be concluded that organizational trust has a positive and significant effect on both job satisfaction, organizational commitment and work engagement. On this basis, hypothesis 7 proposed in this study is declared accepted

Table 3 also shows that job satisfaction has an influence on both organizational commitment and work engagement as proven by test results where job satisfaction has a path coefficient of 0.460, t-statistic of 4.016 (>1.96) with a P-value of 0.000 (< 0.05) on organizational commitment, while job satisfaction on work engagement has a path coefficient of 0.410, t-statistic of 4.160 (> 1.96) with a P-value of 0.000 (< 0.05) which means there is significant influence between job satisfaction and work engagement. Through these findings, it can be confirmed that hypothesis 8 and hypothesis 9 proposed in this study are accepted. Furthermore, related to organizational commitment to work engagement in hypothesis 10, it was found to have

a path coefficient of 0.362, with a P-value of 0.003 (< 0.05), which means there is a significant influence between organizational commitment and work engagement. Based on this, it can be concluded that hypothesis 10 proposed in this study is declared accepted.

Indirect Effect

Based on the results of tests carried out on indirect effects using the SmartPLS Ver, 3 analysis tool, the following results were found.

Table 4: Results of Indirect Effect Testing (Mediation)

Indirect Influence Hypothesis					Path Coefficient	P Values	
H11	Organizational Justice	→	Organizational Trust	→	Organizational Commitment	0.193	0.006
H12	Organizational Justice	→	Job satisfaction	→	Organizational Commitment	0.216	0,000
H13	Organizational Justice	→	Organizational Trust	→	Work Engagement	0.143	0.033
H14	Organizational Justice	→	Job satisfaction	→	Work Engagement	0.193	0,000
H15	Organizational Justice	→	Organizational Commitment	→	Work Engagement	0.101	0.030

Based on table 4, The hypothesis proposed in this research tests the mediating influence of organizational trust on the influence of organizational justice on organizational commitment. has a path coefficient value of 0.193 and a p-value of 0.006 (< 0.05), so it can be concluded that organizational trust mediates the influence of organizational justice on organizational commitment. On this basis, the 11 money hypotheses proposed in this research were declared accepted because they were proven to be true. Then hypothesis 12 was also found to have a path coefficient value of 0.216 and a p-value of 0.000 (< 0.05), so it can be concluded that job satisfaction mediates the influence of organizational justice on organizational commitment. On this basis, hypothesis 12 can also be accepted because it is proven to be true.

In testing the mediation hypothesis of hypothesis 13, hypothesis 14, and hypothesis 15, respectively, it was found that the mediating effect of organizational trust on the influence of organizational justice on work engagement was found to have a path coefficient value of 0.143 and a p-value of 0.033 (< 0, 05), then the mediating effect of job satisfaction on the influence of organizational justice on work engagement has a path coefficient value of 0.193 and a p-value of 0.000 (<0.05), while hypothesis 15 tests the mediating effect of organizational commitment on the influence of Organizational justice on work engagement was found to have a path coefficient of 0.101 and a p-value of 0.030 (< 0.05), so it can be concluded that overall organizational trust, job satisfaction and organizational commitment can mediate the influence of organizational justice on work engagement.

On this basis, hypotheses 13, 14, and 15 proposed in this research are declared accepted. Looking at the existing mediation role, referring to the direct influence of organizational justice on work engagement which is not significant, shows that the mediation role contained in hypotheses 13, 14, and 15 has full mediating properties (full mediation).

CONCLUSION

In general, the findings of this research can be concluded that organizational justice was found to have the greatest role in creating perceptions of trust from members towards their organization and this also influences how organizational commitment and work engagement are possessed by members of the organization. Apart from that, within the scope of police organizations, it was found that organizational justice had no influence on changes in the work engagement of existing personnel. These findings show that in general organizations that are overseen by the government regarding aspects of organizational justice have been partially regulated through statutory regulations, so these findings reveal that the absence of different treatment for the majority of organizational members means that the implementation of organizational justice does not have a direct impact on change. Work engagement behavior.

Furthermore, organizational trust is an important aspect that needs to be considered, which in this research was found to have a good impact in creating job satisfaction felt by organizational members at work. Apart from that, organizational trust is related to the commitment that members of the organization have, where high trust can foster better commitment, as well as the work engagement that is felt, where because of the trust that organizational members have in their organization, they have a strong will to give their all. Energy for work and organizational success. On the other hand, looking at the role of organizational trust in its contribution to supporting organizational justice, it is important for every organization to increase the trust that organizational members have in the organization where they work.

Job satisfaction also plays an important role in that with a feeling of satisfaction a person will be committed and have high dedication to their work, where the findings of this research reveal that job satisfaction is able to provide a strong impetus in creating organizational commitment and work engagement from organizational members. On the other hand, strong efforts to generate better organizational commitment were found to have a more positive impact on the work implementation demonstrated by organizational members. The findings of this research also reveal that high organizational commitment can encourage the creation of better work engagement in supporting organizational members in working and achieving the goals they hope for. Furthermore, mediation testing revealed that organizational trust, job satisfaction and organizational commitment are key factors in efforts to create work engagement behavior in the workplace that is based on fair treatment within the organization.

RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS AND LIMITATIONS

This research provides several interesting contributions both theoretically and practically. Where theoretically, this research proposes a comprehensive research model framework to fill the existing literature gap. Apart from that, this research presents research that supports the literature through analysis of organizational commitment and work engagement in the framework of organizational justice with the result that organizational justice can encourage the creation of organizational commitment, but not work engagement, providing a lot of evidence that organizational justice cannot completely determine every change. Aspects within the organization. This research expands the literature on organizational trust and job satisfaction in that through its support, organizational justice can influence not only organizational

commitment but also changes in work engagement behavior. Furthermore, this research is an effort to support the role of organizational trust and job satisfaction as mediation, where the results of this research show that organizational justice can increase organizational commitment and work engagement through increasing trust and job satisfaction.

The results of this research are very important for the Regional Police of Southeast Sulawesi Province, especially for each work unit within it. It is necessary to optimize the rules and policies for the management of the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police as a whole which is more oriented towards improving organizational aspects that have a direct impact on members of the organization. Through this, it is felt necessary to continue to optimize the aspects of justice provided both organizationally and specifically to members of the organization so that every member of the organization has the awareness that they are an important asset for the organization who can support the running of the organization in accordance with its corridors. Apart from that, it is also hoped that the findings of this research can provide input to the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police, especially in each existing work unit in order to realize high commitment from personnel to their organization and realize their work engagement behavior in providing excellent service and realizing the mission of the police as protectors, protector and community servant.

This research was carried out without limitations. There are several limitations in this research, first, the research carried out could not explore further regarding organizational justice, organizational trust, job satisfaction, organizational commitment and work engagement with in-depth interviews with respondents, thus information about research variables was only obtained based on answers. Existing questionnaire. Second, the data in this study was taken using a survey technique which has limitations in presenting cross-sectional analysis, therefore changes that occur in the research object after that cannot be controlled. Therefore, to identify these changes, further research is needed and retest whether the relationship between existing variables has changed and can use time series data to maximize existing data. Third, this research was limited to the Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police, where conditions will be different from other police organizations in different regions or in different countries. Thus, this can limit the generalizability of the findings of this research. For this reason, it is hoped that future research can test this research model on a wider scope or in police organizations in different regions or countries so that generalization of the findings of this research can be developed.

Based on these limitations, with regard to research development, further research can develop this research with several aspects including: First, further research can test this research model on police organizations in different regions or can test the model on other organizational sectors to increase the generalizability of the findings. this research. Second, the use of data that is more accurate and has a longer time range can make it possible to see comprehensively the changes that occur in carrying out the analysis, therefore it is possible to use time series data to be able to see comprehensively the problems that occur. Third, further research can look separately at the role of organizational justice on work engagement in private sector organizations to see whether existing justice is able to influence the work engagement of organizational members.

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